

FRACTOGRAPHIC INVESTIGATION ON TEMPERATURE-MODIFIED FIBRE/MATRIX INTERFACE OF CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The influence of environment on carbon fibre reinforced composites has attracted widespread attention. Once exposed to high temperature, the subsequent degradation of polymeric matrices as well as fibre/matrix interfaces has a huge impact on relevant mechanical properties. In this study, carbon-epoxy composite coupons were subjected to heat-treatment in a furnace with controlled temperature. Finite element analysis was utilized to pinpoint the appropriate temperature cycle. Heat-treated components were then examined by Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA), interlaminar shear strength and fractographic investigation via scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Although there has been no significant change in interlaminar shear strengths, fractographic morphologies such as shear cusps and crows-feet underwent evident alteration during SEM investigation. Densities and dimensions of crazing, cusps, crows-feet, microcracks and voids on fibre imprints showed substantial reductions as heat-treatment temperatures and duration increased. The results provided beneficial insights to future studies on temperature effects on composite structures of a larger scale.

Figure 1 Fractograph of 225°C heat-treated specimen for 1 min after short beam shear test

Figure 2 Fractograph of 225°C heat-treated specimen for 5 min after short beam shear test

Table 1. Short beam shear strength of as-received and heat-treated specimens in various temperatures

Short beam shear 200-250°C 5 minute heat-treatment test			
Conditioning (No. of specimens)	short-beam strength (MPa)	standard deviation (MPa)	coefficient of variation (%)
As-received (5)	85.62	5.72	6.68
200°C (5)	81.45	2.58	3.17
225°C (5)	80.71	9.55	11.83
250°C (5)	77.49	5.97	7.71